

CYCLOPES - Fighting Cybercrime – Law Enforcement Practitioners’ Network

Deliverable 7.2 Non-EU-Countries Public

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Summary

The purpose of this deliverable is to show that no matter where the activities of the project are conducted, the ethical standards and guidelines of H2020 will be followed. All activities of the CYCLOPES will happen in either EU member country or in the only non-member country of the consortium: the United Kingdom (UK). Therefore, the deliverable focus on presenting the three UK partners (Sheffield Hallam University/CENTRIC, the Home Office, and the College of Policing) alongside with their activities, as well as on the ethical standards and guidelines that they are following. The focus of this deliverable is not to explain what the ethical standards and guidelines of H2020 are, but rather the aim is to see whether the non-EU members are in compliance vis-à-vis the ones of the H2020.

Two main points needs to be mentioned here. First, is that taking into account the nature of the project, being a network activity with only limited amount research activities, there are no critical and/or substantial ethical issues to consider in CYCLOPES. For example, no minors or vulnerable groups involved, no medical research and so on. Despite the project has limited amount of research activities, all research ethical standards will be fulfilled. The main ethical issues in CYCLOPES are related to human participation in different venues, workshops, and contributing to questionnaires and surveys. Thus, for example, there is no intrusive research methods, nor is there any collection of personal information or such. The second point is that the consortium members from UK have a long tradition on what comes to ethics, research ethics alike. Further, UK was for a long time a member state too, and the partners have experience working in EU-funded projects. Thus, following ethical guidelines of H2020 is hardly any problem for them.

As a conclusion from the two points presented above: because of the nature of the project, because of the strong emphasis on ethics of the UK partners, and because of their previous experience on European funded projects there is no doubt that the ethical standards and guidelines of H2020 will be rigorously followed.

Introduction

This document aims to confirm that the ethical standards and guidelines of H2020 will be rigorously applied regardless of the country in which the research is carried out. This document does not present the standards and guidelines *per se*, they should be clear to the partners. The aim is to show that no matter where the activities of the project are conducted, the ethical standards and guidelines of H2020 will be followed. All activities of the CYCLOPES will happen in either EU member country or in the only non-member country of the consortium: the United Kingdom (UK). Therefore, the deliverable focus on presenting the three UK partners (Sheffield Hallam University/CENTRIC, the Home Office, and the College of Policing) alongside with their activities, as well as on the ethical standards and guidelines that they are following.

When presenting the non-EU-countries of a H2020-project, data privacy should normally be addressed too. The reason why this is not done here is simple: the non-EU-countries of this project, the United Kingdom, has agreed with the EU in the Trade and Cooperation Agreement on bridging period, during which the transfer of personal data to the UK may continue under the same conditions as before and during the transition period. This means that, until the end of the bridging period, the same rules apply to the transfer of personal data to the UK as to transfers within the EU.¹ Thus, no need to address this on CYCLOPES yet. However, the bridging period ends on 30 June 2021. After that it is envisaged that the European Commission may issue two data protection adequacy decisions for the UK under the GDPR and the Data Protection Law Enforcement Directive (DPLED).² Nevertheless, this process is still undergoing, and CYCLOPES needs to follow it, and be aware of it.

Structure of the deliverable

The first part of this document introduces the topic of this deliverable, the ethical concerns, and how CYCLOPES addresses it. The second part, presents the consortium members, especially those that are outside the members states. The third part describes the research and other activities the CYCLOPES' non-EU-countries are taking part of, illustrates the possible ethical concerns (or more precisely lack of it), and presents the guiding principles in which the consortium members are committed to. The last part is a short conclusion and so-called future steps.

¹ See, the European Data Protection Board (EDPB): *Statement on the withdrawal of the United Kingdom from the European Union*. Online. Available at: https://edpb.europa.eu/sites/edpb/files/files/file1/edpb_statement_20201215_brexit_updated20210113_en.pdf

² See for example, the European Data Protection Board (EDPB): *Information note on data transfers under the GDPR to the United Kingdom after the transition period*. Online. Available at: https://edpb.europa.eu/sites/edpb/files/files/file1/edpb_informationnote_20201215_transferstoukaftertransitionperiod_updated20210113_en.pdf, and the European Data Protection Board (EDPB): *Recommendations 01/2020 on measures that supplement transfer tools to ensure compliance with the EU level of protection of personal data, Version 2.0, Adopted on 18 June 2021*. Online. Available at: https://edpb.europa.eu/our-work-tools/our-documents/recommendations/recommendations-012020-measures-supplement-transfer_en

The Ethical Standards

This chapter presents very briefly the ethical standards and guidelines of H2020 that will be rigorously applied regardless of the country in which the research is carried out. The reason for perhaps lesser attention to the standards themselves given here than a reader might expect is that this deliverable is not about the standards and guidelines as such: they are merely a reference to the ones of the non-EU members.

Either way, by signing the CYCLOPES Grant Agreement, all the beneficiaries have agreed to carry out the action in compliance with:

- a) ethical principles (including the highest standards of research integrity), and
- b) applicable international, EU and national law.

For example, all beneficiaries agreed not to:

- a) aim at human cloning for reproductive purposes;
- b) intend to modify the genetic heritage of human beings which could make such changes heritable (with the exception of research relating to cancer treatment of the gonads, which may be financed), or
- c) intend to create human embryos solely for the purpose of research or for the purpose of stem cell procurement, including by means of somatic cell nuclear transfer.

Above would be highly unlikely taken into consideration the aim of CYCLOPES and its activities. However, the beneficiaries must respect the fundamental principle of research integrity nevertheless. Thus for example principles stated e.g. in the *European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity*³ must be followed, and the principles do apply to our project no matter how insignificant they seem to be in practice. Thus, although CYCLOPES is not a research project *per se*, and the practical implications of the ethical standards plays a very minor role in the activities, CYCLOPES do have a research component in it, and therefore, CYCLOPES will be in compliance with the following fundamental principles:

- **reliability** in ensuring the quality of research reflected in the design, the methodology, the analysis and the use of resources;
- **honesty** in developing, undertaking, reviewing, reporting and communicating research in a transparent, fair and unbiased way;
- **respect** for colleagues, research participants, society, ecosystems, cultural heritage and the environment;
- **accountability** for the research from idea to publication, for its management and organisation, for training, supervision and mentoring, and for its wider impacts and means that beneficiaries must ensure that persons carrying out research tasks follow the good research practices and refrain from the research integrity violations described in the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity.

³ *European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity of ALLEA (All European Academies)* Available online at: http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/hi/h2020-ethics_code-of-conduct_en.pdf

Member states & Non-Member States

The requirement and obligation to follow rigorously the ethical standards does not change depending the location of the activities – in European Union or in a third country. Thus, a critical element of this deliverable is to examine where the activities of CYCLOPES are to be carried out (traditional research is much missing in CYCLOPES, but this covers also other activities e.g. workshops, events etc.).

According to the Grant Agreement and especially on its annexes the Description of Action (DoA), Part A and B, the activities to be held in CYCLOPES will happen in either EU member state, or in the only Non-EU-Country of CYCLOPES, the United Kingdom (UK), home of three consortium members.

The list of the CYCLOPES partners is presented the table below, and the three UK partners emphasised.

#	Participant Legal Name	Country
1	STOWARZYSZENIE POLSKA PLATFORMA BEZPIECZENSTWA WEWNETRZNEGO	PL
2	NEDERLANDSE ORGANISATIE VOOR TOEGEPAST NATUURWETENSCHAPPELIJK ONDERZOEK TNO	NL
3	SHEFFIELD HALLAM UNIVERSITY	UK
4	STICHTING DUTCH INSTITUTE FOR TECHNOLOGY, SAFETY & SECURITY	NL
5	IANUS CONSULTING LTD	CY
6	CYBERCRIME RESEARCH INSTITUTE GMBH	DE
7	AUSTRIAN STANDARDS INTERNATIONAL	AT
8	ZENTRALE STELLE FÜR INFORMATIONSTECHNIK IM SICHERHEITSBEREICH	DE
9	LAUREA-AMMATTIKORKEAKOULU OY	FI
10	UNIVERSITY COLLEGE DUBLIN, NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND, DUBLIN	IE
11	HOME OFFICE	UK
12	PROVINCIAL POLICE HEADQUARTERS IN GDANSK	PL
13	MINISTRY OF INTERIOR	HR
14	GLAVNA DIREKTSIA BORBA S ORGANIZIRANATA PRESTUPNOST	BG
15	POLISMYNDIGHETEN SWEDISH POLICE AUTHORITY	SE
16	MINISTERIO DEL INTERIOR	ESP
17	POLICE FEDERALE BELGE	BE
18	IEKSLIETU MINISTRIJAS VALSTS POLICIJA STATE POLICE OF THE MINISTRY OF INTERIOR	LV
19	COLLEGE OF POLICING	UK
20	THE NATIONAL POLICE OF THE NETHERLANDS	NL
21	MALTA POLICE FORCE	MT

Due to a long standing cooperation with the Commission, the EU member states have in practice harmonised their ethical standards applicable to EU research. And, since for very long, UK was a member state too, the ethical standards are equivalent to the European Union's. Nevertheless, here below in next the three sub-chapters are presented shortly the three partners from non-member state together with the activities they are taking part, i.e. the *Sheffield Hallam University / CENTRIC*, the *Home Office*, and the *College of Policing*, all from the United Kingdom, as stated earlier, and their ethical base. The information was gathered by

inquiries done in June 2021 in a form of email exchange with the representatives of the CYCLOPES' UK partners and the author of this deliverable.

Sheffield Hallam University / CENTRIC

CENTRIC (Centre of Excellence in Terrorism, Resilience, Intelligence & Organised Crime Research) is a multidisciplinary, security-focused research centre located at Sheffield Hallam University. The strategic aim of CENTRIC is to develop and facilitate the collaboration between four key stakeholders in the security domain: Citizens, Law Enforcement Agencies (LEA's), Industry and Academia. Consequently, CENTRIC is able to provide solutions to some of Europe's most pressing contemporary security challenges through the delivery of ground-breaking research, advanced technological capabilities, professional expertise and training. CENTRIC builds on over six years of work by a range of colleagues across government, academia and the private sector. The CENTRIC team has experience of more than 20 independent, EU, and International research projects.

CENTRIC will **lead on WP3**: Research, innovation and market watch and deliver the main research tasks by designing the methodology to identify existing research solutions that tackle the cyber challenges identified through the workshops and performing the corresponding baseline research.

CENTRIC will be involved also in:

- WP1: task 1.2. Technical Organisation, Coordination, Quality Control and Risk Management
- WP2: task 2.4 Development of European foresight reports for Member States LEAs (Leader)
- WP5: task 5.1. CYCLOPES community building methodology and framework, task 5.2. Dialogue with other practitioners' networks and stakeholders
- WP6: task 6.1 Communication and dissemination plan, task 6.2. Exploitation plan, task 6.3. Communication and dissemination channels and materials

The anticipated work of CENTRIC in this project involves research activities such as building proper methodology for conducting different activities, and also management, dissemination and communication. None of the work will involve humans as research subject *per se*. The interest is thus not on the person itself, but on what the competent healthy adults participants can voluntarily disclose from professional point-of-view.

CENTRIC takes research ethics and standards very seriously. They follow the guidelines, policy, and procedures of Sheffield Hallam University (SHU), manifested in *Research Ethics Policy and Procedures* compiled by the University Research Ethics Committee.⁴

SHU and thus CENTRIC is committed to ensuring that they act in accordance with the principles set out in the UK's national policy statement on research integrity, the *Concordat to*

⁴ Research Ethics Policy and Procedures, 8th Edition (2017). Available online at: <https://www.shu.ac.uk/~media/home/research/files/ethics/research-ethics-policy-and-procedures-v8-2017.pdf?la=en&hash=4589AB73F921D0AFC7B45DC8F4DA977F>

*Support Research Integrity*⁵, too. The Concordat outlines what is expected of the researcher and the employers to ensure the highest standards in research. A testimony of the commitment of the Sheffield Hallam University to the principles of the Concordat SHU has been acknowledged by receiving the *HR Excellence in Research Award* from the European Commission.⁶ Furthermore, the approach of SHU to promoting research integrity is recognised by the European Science Foundation (ESF).

Sheffield Hallam University has a data protection officer and a formal ethical approval process for research activities which CENTRIC will follow. CENTRIC will adhere to the University's research ethics and data protection guidelines as well as UK code of practice for research.⁷

Before commencing any research with human subjects, CENTRIC will submit a research ethics application that covers their activities within CYCLOPES to ensure that research participants are informed and treated appropriately, and their rights regarding their participation and use of their data is respected. CENTRIC will ensure that formal approval through the university ethics process is received and any recommendations are implemented in advance of the research activities.⁸

The University's existing ethics policies and procedures are designed to encourage the highest research standards with regard to:

- Selecting, informing and protecting research participants: e.g. applying appropriate sampling procedures; avoiding physical risk or emotional harm (especially in relation to 'vulnerable' categories, such as children, the elderly and people in care); observing the participants' right to withdraw, and debriefing them appropriately.
- Obtaining participants' informed consent and being able to thoroughly justify (both morally and legally) any deliberate forms of 'covert' and/or 'deception'.
- Observing principles of confidentiality and anonymity.
- Storing data securely and disposing of it appropriately as required.
- Ensuring the integrity and quality of the research: e.g. considering relevant sponsorship issues and possible impacts of the research; employing the most appropriate methods and design; ensuring that researchers have suitable skills and expertise; acknowledging possible conflicts of interest.
- Fulfilling any legal obligations: e.g. non-infringement of copyrighted material; following the appropriate rules and principles of data protection.

⁵ More details from the website of Universities UK the *Concordat to Support Research Integrity*, <https://www.universitiesuk.ac.uk/policy-and-analysis/reports/Documents/2019/the-concordat-to-support-research-integrity.pdf>

⁶ See, <https://www.shu.ac.uk/research/quality/ethics-and-integrity/the-concordat-to-support-the-career-development-of-researchers>

⁷ See, <https://ukrio.org/publications/code-of-practice-for-research/>

⁸ See, for more information at: <https://www.shu.ac.uk/research/ethics-integrity-and-practice>

Home Office, UK

The UK Home Office (HO) is a ministerial department with 35,000 staff, responsible for Home Affairs within the UK. It is the lead government department for immigration and passports, borders, drugs policy, crime, fire, counter-terrorism and police. The department keeps the UK safe through three strands of policy and operational delivery covering Homeland Security, Public Safety and Borders Immigration and Citizenship.

Home Office Science Advisory Council (HOSAC) that provide independent advice on the use of science across the Home Office⁹ and the *Biometrics and Forensics Science Ethics Group (BFEG)* that provides independent ethical advice to Home Office ministers on issues related to the collection, use, and retention of biometric and forensic material. The BFEG also advises on ethical issues in the use of large and complex data sets and projects using explainable data-driven technology.¹⁰

Home Office Science¹¹ has a vibrant science and technology programme that supports the delivery of Home Office priorities through the commissioning of science and technology projects focussed on public safety. The HO Science Commissioning Hub works with policy makers and end users to identify the policy and operational challenges which are converted into thematic science and technology development programmes.

Home Office Science is the primary science and technology interface between Home Office ministers, policy makers, operational delivery partners and the suppliers of science and technological solutions. Understanding the policy and its link to the operational context allows HO Science to operate where others cannot for reasons of impartiality, national security or market failure.

HO Science supports the full range of Home Office interests in policing, tackling crime, counter terrorism, border security and controlling immigration. The extensive skills and expertise, coupled with access to industry, academic and international networks ensures that the most appropriate solutions are commissioned in order to address operational challenges.

The Home Office has significant experience in the management of both national and international networking activities. It's role includes the application of digital technology in public safety and it will be involved in leading the workshop development and delivery throughout the duration of the project. The Home Office will provide the link into UK and international operational law enforcement communities through extensive strategic links.

The HO Science Commissioning Hub will be **responsible for WP2**: Identification of practitioners' capabilities, gaps and requirements (practitioner workshops) in the project as well as supporting all other work packages.

⁹ For more details, see the Home Office Science Advisory Council webpage at:

<https://www.gov.uk/government/groups/home-office-science-advisory-council>

¹⁰See, *Biometrics and Forensics Ethics Group, Code Of Practice Including Terms of Reference & Working Protocol*. Available online at:

[https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/754219/20181106 - BFEG code of practice including terms of reference and working protocol.pdf](https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/754219/20181106_-_BFEG_code_of_practice_including_terms_of_reference_and_working_protocol.pdf)

¹¹ For more details on Home Office Science, see

https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/204674/intro-to-cast-may13.pdf

HO will be involved also in:

- WP1: task 1.2. Technical Organisation, Coordination, Quality Control and Risk Management, task 1.3. Management of Security related issues
- WP3: task 3.3. Joint live exercises – based on realistic scenarios, task 3.4. Continuous monitoring of LEA needs and requirement and validation
- WP4: task 4.3. Annual standardisation workshops, task 4.4. Innovation uptake recommendations
- WP5: task 5.1. CYCLOPES community building methodology and framework, task 5.2. Dialogue with other practitioners' networks and stakeholders
- WP6: task 6.1 Communication and dissemination plan, task 6.2. Exploitation plan, task 6.3. Communication and dissemination channels and materials, task 6.5. Annual dissemination event

HO will work mainly on things related with the practitioner workshops. Thus, the activities are relating to managing those events but also acquiring information from the participants: again competent healthy adults acting voluntarily, expressing their professional point-of-view. Thus, no ethically challenging human participation involved.

As stated earlier, the Home Office is a ministerial department of state with responsibilities for public safety. Whilst the principal focus of the department is not a research related function, it carries out research related activities that comply with the *UK Government Codes of Practice for Scientific Advisory Committees* with specific attention to the *Universal Ethical Code of Rigour, Respect and Responsibility* (see *Code of Practice for Scientific Advisory Committees: CoPSAC 2011* (publishing.service.gov.uk) Annex B).¹²

The main points from the CoPSAC's Annex B to be highlighted are:

- Rigour, honesty and integrity
 - Act with skill and care in all scientific work. Maintain up to date skills and assist their development in others.
 - Take steps to prevent corrupt practices and professional misconduct. Declare conflicts of interest.
 - Be alert to the ways in which research derives from and affects the work of other people, and respect the rights and reputations of others.
- Respect for life, the law and the public good
 - Ensure that your work is lawful and justified.
 - Minimise and justify any adverse effect your work may have on people, animals and the natural environment.
- Responsible communication: listening and informing

¹²See the [Code of Practice for Scientific Advisory Committees: CoPSAC 2011 \(publishing.service.gov.uk\)](http://publishing.service.gov.uk).

- o Seek to discuss the issues that science raises for society. Listen to the aspirations and concerns of others.
- o Do not knowingly mislead, or allow others to be misled, about scientific matters. Present and review scientific evidence, theory or interpretation honestly and accurately.

Above is of course relevant and desirable when carrying out activities in CYCLOPES, also important are the phrases of the same documents underlining the obligations to follow ethical standards and guidelines set by funders, as well as international conventions, treaties and laws, thus making the following of the Ethical Standards and Guidelines of H2020 fundamental.¹³

In addition to complying with the *UK Government Codes of Practice for Scientific Advisory Committees*, the Home Office has a number of independent bodies that monitor the scientific and ethical issues regarding scientific activities across the Home Office. These include the

College of Policing

The College of Policing was established in 2012 as the professional body for everyone who works for the police service in England and Wales. The purpose of the College is to provide those working in policing with the skills and knowledge necessary to prevent crime, protect the public, and secure public trust.

The College has three complementary functions:

Knowledge – they develop the research and infrastructure for improving evidence of 'what works'. Over time, this will ensure that policing practice and standards are based on knowledge, rather than custom and convention.

Education – they support the development of individuals in policing. We set educational requirements to assure the public of the quality and consistency of policing skills and we facilitate the academic accreditation and recognition of policing expertise.

Standards – they draw on the best available evidence of 'what works' to set standards in policing for forces and individuals. Examples include our *Authorised Professional Practice* (APP) and peer reviews.

Their role in carrying out research and turning it into educational products and standards means that we are ideally placed to support work packages in the proposal that address:

- research, innovation and market scanning;
- standardisation and market uptake;
- societal, ethical and legal framework.

¹³ Ibid. "There are already powerful incentives for individuals and for institutions to adhere to the principles set out in these guidelines. These include: the high professional and ethical standards upheld by the scientific community; structures put in place by employers, professional bodies and funders to enforce these standards; and national and international conventions, treaties and laws."

College of Policing will be involved in:

- WP3: task 3.1. Development of specific methodology for conducting research, innovation and market watch, task 3.2. Mapping of existing and forthcoming solutions against the requirements identified in WP2, task 3.3. Joint live exercises – based on realistic scenarios, task 3.4. Continuous monitoring of LEA's needs and requirement, including validation
- WP4: task 4.1. WP4 Terms of reference. Task 4.2. Standardisation recommendations, task 4.3. Annual standardisation workshops, task 4.4. Innovation uptake recommendations
- WP5: task 5.2. Community building, dialogue with other practitioners' networks and stakeholders
- WP6: task 6.1 Communication and dissemination plan, task 6.3. Communication and dissemination channels and materials, task 6.4. Webinars
- WP7: task 7.2. Comprehensive Assessment of Social, Ethical and Legal Issues Related to Cybercrime, task 7.3. Recommendations for Training and Best Practices to be Introduced and Used by LEAs

The College of Policing states on their webpage on ethics the following: "Ensuring that the people who work for the police uphold the values of the service, strive to do the right thing in all situations and have the public's confidence."¹⁴ Above statement, and the related specific section of the webpages dedicated to ethics is a strong indication that the College of Policing has put ethics in the centre of their activities.

The main ethical guidance and standards that the College of Policing both promotes and follows – disclosed for example in *Code of Ethics*¹⁵ and its supporting documents¹⁶ – are obviously related more with day-to-day police work and policing than with research or related activities. However, the nine principles named in the Code, 1) *accountability*, 2) *integrity*, 3) *openness*, 4) *fairness*, 5) *leadership*, 6) *respect*, 7) *honesty*, 8) *objectivity*, and 9) *selflessness*, are all transferable to the principles of the *European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity of ALLEA* presented in the beginning of this deliverable.

Besides the Code of Ethics, the College of Policing is committed to enhance their knowledge and evidence base, as well as into developing a framework for continuous professional development. These guiding principles too – i.e. pursuing to gain more knowledge – are

¹⁴ See the webpage of the College of Policing, <https://www.college.police.uk/ethics> [Accessed 1.6.2021]

¹⁵ *The Code of Ethics*. Available online at: <http://www.college.police.uk/en/20989.htm>

¹⁶ *The Code of Ethics – Briefing Note July 2014*. Available online at: https://paas-s3-broker-prod-lon-6453d964-1d1a-432a-9260-5e0ba7d2fc51.s3.eu-west-2.amazonaws.com/s3fs-public/2021-02/code_supportingdocs_briefingnote.pdf; *The Code of Ethics – Assessment Guide*. Available online at: https://paas-s3-broker-prod-lon-6453d964-1d1a-432a-9260-5e0ba7d2fc51.s3.eu-west-2.amazonaws.com/s3fs-public/2021-02/code_supportingdocs_assessmentguide.pdf; *The Code of Ethics – Organisational Model*. Available online at: https://paas-s3-broker-prod-lon-6453d964-1d1a-432a-9260-5e0ba7d2fc51.s3.eu-west-2.amazonaws.com/s3fs-public/2021-02/code_supportingdocs_organisationalmodel.pdf; and *The Code of Ethics – Reading list*. Available online at: https://paas-s3-broker-prod-lon-6453d964-1d1a-432a-9260-5e0ba7d2fc51.s3.eu-west-2.amazonaws.com/s3fs-public/2021-02/code_of_ethics_readinglist.pdf.

fundamental in securing ethical standards of research and related activities, since they lay down the primary importance of activities in research.

Conclusion

Taking into account the different aspects presented in this deliverable, namely the fact that:

- all the activities of CYCLOPES will be done in either a member state or in the UK;
- the rigorous commitments of the UK partners to various ethical code of practices;
- the nature of the project, being a network activity with only limited amount research activities, (no critical and/or substantial ethical issues to consider: no intrusive research methods, nor is there any collection of personal information or such, no minors, vulnerable groups etc.); and that
- the main ethical issues are related to human participation in different venues, workshops, and contributing to questionnaires and surveys (always voluntary, consent mandatory, see D7.1)

it can be concluded with confidence that regardless the country in which the activities of CYCLOPES are carried out, they are indeed in accordance with the ethical standards and guidelines of H2020.

Of course, putting the ethical standards and guidelines in practice needs work too, and for this, pivotal is the active involvement in ethics work of the whole consortium, and especially the Ethics Manager and the Ethical Advisory Board.